

“Impact of Organization Justice on the Job Satisfaction of Employees among Academia of Higher Education Institution (HEIs), Sindh”

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Abstract:

The paper Examine the impact of organization justice on the job satisfaction of employees among academia of Higher Education Institution (HEIs), Sindh. The study observed the connection between organizational justice comprised by two major components including distributive justice and procedural justice and job satisfaction between academic staff. The investigation of study based on some selected public colleges and universities in khairpur. For the collection of data questioners distributed among responded, total 30 peoples were chosen as sample, from which 15 responded selected for open ended interviews and 15 for survey by using “Likert scale” based on “strongly agree” to “strongly disagree”. Data relate to ask the responded whether somewhat really fair or not .For this regard we use qualitative and quantitative study. With the help of QSR Nvivo 10 software we run the three main Queries include Text Search Query, Word Frequency Query and Matrix query. The findings also suggested that this was positive association between organizational justice dimensions (distributive justice and procedural justice) and job satisfaction but there is no any relationship between personal traits like gender like age, gender and nature of job with employee’s job satisfaction. The paper limitation is only give information about Impact of Organization justice on employee’s job satisfaction among Academic staff of HEIs of khairpur Sindh Pakistan. The further study can be taken through increasing the size of sample and target area.

Key words: Organization justice, Job satisfaction, Higher Education

1. Introduction

The main theme of this paper is Organizational Justice especially in Higher Education Institute (HEIs) of Sindh. It is very critical elements for any organization to run effectively. If the organization are going to compromise on justice especially service related like educational sectors of Pakistan ultimately will fall down in progress and performance. Organizational justice (OJ) is prime element which focus on fairness especially at workplace and the job satisfaction of employees. For this concerns, the elementary purpose of Study is to identify the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction between academic staff of Higher Education Institute (HEIs) in Pakistan.

It is important to determine why peoples are fairly treated or organization applied unfair means and treated them unfairly in service oriented organization. Most of the justice researchers understand their importance and uses in different context, as organization based on social criteria where the employees are perform physical and mental efforts and their satisfaction is mandatory for achieve efficiency and effectiveness. Most of the global organizations trying to identify that which factor influencing on the performance of employees and their job satisfaction because both are key variables that ultimately affecting on organization performance. According to (Fatt, Khin and Heng 2010) recommended that higher job satisfaction of employees should be there because they believe on organization that provide them prestige, future benefit and attention toward their qualitative work.

The role of educational institution is to create prosper and healthy education to the students and well trained faculty in order to support our youth. Educational institution need the capable and strong academia to develop the better educational skills. If education sector want to become prosper they never neglect the importance of Human resource to provide them all kind of benefit’s either monetary or non-monetary rewards and also never neglect the justice criteria because every employee in favor of justice in work related criteria either in the form of distributive or based on procedural justice to make them not just satisfied but also committed with organization

2. The objectives of the study

The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To examine the level of organizational justice by academic staff of HEIs in Pakistan
2. To find out the relationship between organizational justice and employees job satisfaction among academia of higher educational institute of Sindh.

3. Problem Definition

Due to lack of research on Impact of Organization justice on employees’ job satisfaction among Academic staff of Higher Education (HEIs), especially in Sindh Pakistan. For this regard the central research questions of this research would be:

1. *How the organizational justice effect on employees job satisfaction among academic staff of HEIs in Pakistan?*
2. *Does the organizational justice dimensions (Distributive and Procedural) have influence on employees job Satisfaction of academia?*
3. *Does there any relationship between personal traits e.g. age, gender and nature of job and employees job satisfaction*

4. Literature Review

4.1 Organizational Justice

The word “Justice” refer to the quality of being fair. The origin of justice theory proposed by Greek Philosopher “Plato”. Justice refer to the ideas based on the right decisions and actions related with equity, fairness, laws, religion and ethics. The concept of organizational justice (OJ) was elevated from organization as reward and punishment by adding some rules and procedures by (Dendr, Tebankaly, 2013.5777). The qualitative studies of organizational justice based on certain laws, that link the fair treatment of perception with justice (Zapata et al, 19 1:21).Some Qualitative researchers suggest that the organizational justice indicate the relationship between knowledge sharing and components of organization justice by (Yasil and Derli, 2013.1).Organizational justice based on how any employee judge the attitude and behavior of other employees and organizational behavior toward them. (Aydin & Kepenekci, 2008) recommended that the organizational productivity and job satisfaction are basic elements of organization justice.

Organizational justice relate with the feelings or expression expose by the employees actions against the organization, if perceived job justice is more, the tendency of job leave reduces by (Yarmohammadian et al, 2012. 2). According to Rastgar et al. (2012), Organizational Justice describe the fairness in the workplace. The justice theories suggested that the perception of justice is essential determinant for individual decisions and reaction of their decisions by (Camgoz & Karapinar, 2011).There is a positive relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction by Rezaiean et al., (2010). Alam (2010) recommended that employees decisions related with leaving the job can be reduce when there job satisfaction increases. Lambert (et al.2010) find the relationship between organizational justice elements and approaches with job leave and burnout. The felling of injustice increase the burnout and employees increasing their attention toward job leaves.

In educational contexts organizational justice also mandatory to know how academic staff treated fairly concern with their job satisfaction or commitment with the work. Zaman, Ali and Ali (2010) research based on organizational justice dimensions, organizational commitment and job satisfaction. , Bakhshi, Kumar and Rani (2009) conducted research in medical college employees and reported that there is a positive relationship between organizational justice dimension (distributive justice and procedural justice) with performance, job satisfaction, and commitment. The educational sectors must strive the key variables (Employees job performance and job satisfaction) that impact the performance of organization, and create the harmony between the organization justice dimension and variables.

Hassan and Hashim (2011) perceive Malaysian higher education institutions where they found the perceptions differences between national and emigrated academic staff related with organizational justice and how OJ shape job satisfaction, turnovers, job outcomes, commitments etc. Employees who fairly rewarded for their work feel more satisfied they ensure that the reward is a great Contribution by the organization, this treatments create commitment toward the organization and increase productivity and rates of retention by (Fatt, Khin and Heng 2010). Organizational justice has cover up to forty years and there dimension (distributive, procedural, and interactional) include different theories in every field of business. The work of distributive and procedural justice in higher education institute is to enhance the fair system which increase the productivity of educational sectors.

4.1.1 Distributive Justice

Distributive Justice is the first dimension of Organizational justice refer the perceive fairness in terms of reward or resource received by employees (Camgoz & Karapinar, 2011). The origin of distributed justice based on equity theory of Adam (Adams, 1963) that Perceptions of injustice are source of motivation for individual after this theory classical theory describe the distributive justices on the basis of two term, input (time, resources, efforts, experiences, education,) and outputs (pay, promotion, recognition, status, reward). There are three broad dimensions of OJ like distributive, interactional and procedural by (Martinez-tur et al., 2006; Yalmaz & Tasdan, 2009). Fairness of outcome refer to the pay and promotion (Wang, 2010). (Zapata et al, 2013.1) suggested that the distributive justice related with fairness and equity of rules.

Outcome may distributed on the basis of fairness related with need (e.g. urgency) or equal contribution (to each in same), unfair distribution of reward related with work input create tension. It is reality that not all organization follow similar policies to distribute their resources, allocation of outcomes in workplace can be change like less fair system or not all workers equally treated. In the field of education distributive justice based on employees thinking how they are treated in the organization in comparison of other members of faculty.(Saunders & Thornhill, 2004) propose the distributive justice as fair decision taking by organization toward their staff. (Greenberg & Baron, 2008) refer that distributive justice means to create justice in organization that people belief that they are receiving fair outcome of their work e.g., salary and recognition. McFaline (2010), state that the distributive justice function in any field is like as a mediator in relation between other dimensions e.g. work relation with staff members, commitments concern with job, and leader-member interchanging.

4.1.2 Procedural Justice

Procedural Justice is the Second dimension of Organizational justice relate the fair procedures of practices that will be accepted by employees related with the benefits. Distributive justice relate with satisfaction relate with function of outcome, but the procedural justice relate with function of process. It's associated with the employee's perception that how they are paid by organization (Till & Karren, 2011). Most research based theories suggested that procedures should implemented without any self-interest, it's should be based on correct information. (Jafari et al., 2011) recommended that individual perceive fairness related with increase in pay, job satisfaction as well as promotion. The procedural justice can be examine by (Lau and Moser, 2008) in behavioral context based on nonfinancial performance measures. Employee's behavior would be positive if they will be treated fair and when their performance evaluated fairly. The two dimension (distributive justice & procedural justice) link of OJ and job performance can be examine by Nasurdin and Khuan (2011).

4.2 Job Satisfaction

Certain research has been conducted in the context of job satisfaction, it is a critical how to attract and retain well-qualified staff. Job satisfaction based on attitude that people have. This attitude based on their job or about organization where they perform. Russo (2010: online) define that for academic staff of higher education institute big driver is salary for job satisfaction.

Mothman (2009: 3) recommended that it is crucial for educational sectors to determine the job satisfaction and dissatisfaction because these aspects have influence on employee's productivity, performance of employees, motivation as well as the performance of the institution. Research conducted by Khalid & Irshad (2010) that public sector employees satisfaction is more than the private sectors.

Alexander (2010), Brown (2009), and Eldred (2010) suggested that teacher's job satisfaction affected by leadership style of administrator. (Creasy, Stull, & Peck, 2009) define that a level where employees have positive attitude toward the job is called job satisfaction. (Cowan, Johnson, Craven, & Marsh, 2008) define that job satisfaction can be divided into two dimension: intrinsic (e.g. job skills, job complexity, challenges, responsibilities etc.) and extrinsic (e.g. benefits, wages etc.) employee's experience more job satisfaction who have permanent employment than those who are appointed on contract by Morris and Venkatesh (2010: 83). Abdullah et al (2009: 123) recommended that employees who have job satisfaction or job dissatisfaction is the outcome or level of work related stress experience by staff. Abdullah, Ahsan, Shah Alam and Yong Gun Fie (2009: 121) proposed that employees who have high level of stress caused by job insecurity, salary problems, or problems with co-workers/colleagues experience high job dissatisfaction, that create fatigue and burnout. That reduce productivity and negative influence on organization.

5. Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework have much attention on organizational justice and job satisfaction among academia argue certain factors in educational context. Many studies identify that perception of individual about fairness were affective as well as distinguished event by (Rupp & Spencer, 2006). We also determine level of job satisfaction or dissatisfaction on the bases of salary, reward, recognition and other personal traits e.g. age, sex and nature of job. Our findings is relate to Herzberg two factors theory according to the book of management by (Coutland L.Bovee, John V.Thill, Marian Burk Wood, George P.Dovel, 2000), According to which motivated factors are recognition and hygiene factors are salary. Our finding also analyses that job satisfaction are more in permeant faculty members as compare to contractual work. The aim of this research is to study about the impact of organizational justice on employee's job satisfaction. For the relationship we use independent variables are organizational justice and dependent

variable are job satisfaction. The influence of independent variable can be analysed by two constraints i.e. distributive justice and procedural justice on job satisfaction that is dependent variable. Our study focus on how the justice related to the organization and how the organization related to employees job satisfaction. Here is the simple framework that shows the relationship between organizational justice and employee's job satisfaction.

6. Hypotheses of the Study

On the basis of literature review following null hypothesis proposed by researcher as given below:

1. H1: There is significant relationship between organizational justice dimensions (Distributive and Procedural) and employees job satisfaction
2. H2: There is no significant relationship between personal traits (age, gender and nature of job) and employees job satisfaction

6.1 Hypotheses Testing

First Hypothesis Test

There is significant relationship between organizational justice dimensions (Distributive and Procedural) and employee's job satisfaction

Organizational Justice	Job Satisfaction
Distributive justice	42.59%
Procedural justice	57.41%

Second Hypothesis Test

There is no significant relationship between personal traits (age, gender and nature of job) and employee's job satisfaction

H2 a: There is no significant relationship between personal traits like age and employee's job satisfaction

Person Age Group	Job satisfaction
20-29	100%
30-39	100%
40-50	100%
50 and above	100%

H2 b: There is no significant relationship between personal traits like gender and employee’s job satisfaction

Gender	Job Satisfaction
Male	100%
Female	100%

H2 c: There is no significant relationship between personal traits like nature of job and employee’s job satisfaction

Nature of Job	Job satisfaction
Lecturer	100%
Assistant professor	100%
Associate Professor	100%
Professor	100%

Research Model

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Population & Sample

The aim of study of this article is to examine the impact of Organization justice on employee's job satisfaction among academic staff Higher education institution HEIs, Sindh Pakistan. For this regard we were selected just a single city called khairpur Mir's. The total 40 respondent were selected out of which 30 respondent given responses. 15 responded provide detail information by using open ended interviews questions and 15 responses were selected on the bases of survey. The data were collected from public sector of Higher education institution.

Research Instrument

To measure Organization justice and its impact on job satisfaction among academic staff the questionnaire use for research study for this purpose two major dimension of organizational justice(Distributive and Procedural) and job satisfaction were used and 27 items were selected for this regards. To measure the responses of impact of organization justice dimension and job satisfaction in public educational institute five point "Likert Scale" ranging from 1 to 5 from Strongly agree=1, Agree=2, Neutral=3, Disagree=4, Strongly Disagree=5 were used for survey responses. For checking questioner reliability we test responses statistically by SPSS version 21, the scale show validity and reliability score 0.9. but for interview responses we use QSR NVivo 10 were we run the three

queries include Text Search Query, Word Frequency Query and Matrix query.

Findings and results:

The data collected on the bases of surveys and interviews. Results analysis based on organization justice that influence on job satisfaction on employees. Most of the responded recommended that there is unfair distribution of rewards, pay and strong working conditions and reward policies influences on job satisfaction of employees. Strong policies somehow influences on the employees performance and job satisfaction. Through analysis of results our finding decliner that organization justice dimension including distributive justice show 42.59% relation with job satisfaction while Procedural justice show 54.41%. Results can be find by using Matrix query in NVivo 10 software. 13 responded recommended that they are satisfied from job out of which 8 responded recommended that there is unfair distribution of pay and high work load affect their performance 9 responded suggested that there is influences of procedural justice in the organization. The results also declare that there is no any connection between personal trait like age, gender, nature of job and job satisfaction.

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Appendix

1. Word Frequency Query (*cluster Analysis*)

Word Cloud

Tree Map

Word Frequency

agree	teachers	teacher	disagree	employer	academic	member	knowledge	provide	pay	consider	friendly	new	proud	reward	college	earn		
		think	work	made	role	interviewed	interview	techniques	skills	neutral	name	student	white	ahmed	board	guinar	imran	
job	teaching																	
		justice	strongly	decision	faculty	field	question	profession	feel	satisfac								
						information	section	properly	try	system								
yes	satisfied	students	fair	staff	use			institution	understa	time	quite	like	accord	mostly	teach	additi	make	relatic
						different	class	organiza	universit	choice	situation	nida	ambree	aids	way	get	sanar	see

2. Matrix Query for Age

For Gender

For Nature of job

Text Search Query

References	Coverage
25	2.43%
21	1.90%
19	2.25%
19	2.08%
19	2.19%
19	2.17%
19	2.38%
19	2.40%
18	2.11%
18	2.15%
17	2.12%
17	1.94%
17	2.12%
16	1.67%
15	1.78%